

The Potential for Community Tourism Development in Phu Dinh Commune, Dinh Hoa District, Thai Nguyen Province

Nguyen Thi Bich Hanh¹, Mai Thi Lan Anh², Nguyen Thi Hong Vien³, Nguyen Thi Dong⁴, Nguyen Thu Huyen⁵, Chu Thi Hong Huyen⁶

^{1,2,3,4,5,6} Thai Nguyen University of Sciences, Thai Nguyên University

ABSTRACT: Research on the potential of community-based tourism development in Phu Dinh Commune, Dinh Hoa District, Thai Nguyen Province, is essential because the commune has started to have community-based tourism households. In this study, we collected data by surveying tourists, authorities, and local people. We analyzed the data and made judgments about the needs of tourists from visitors' evaluations, local people's understanding, and difficulties with community-based tourism development activities. The results showed tremendous potential for community-based tourism development in Phu Dinh Commune. The potential for historical-cultural tourism has a significant position now, a prerequisite to attracting tourists to Phu Dinh. Besides, the natural tourism potential is also unique and attractive to tourists. To promote the above tourism potentials for community-based tourism development, it is necessary to have investment support in terms of capital, methods, and fostering knowledge of community-based tourism development for local people to attract tourists to visit historical and cultural sites (basically just a day visit). The tourists can both visit the Dinh Hoa Safety Area National Relic (An Toan Khu - ATK) and combine community-based tourism development (increasing the length of stay of tourists from going to the same day (up to 2-3 days).

To achieve these results, it is necessary to converge factors such as policies to support and promote Phu Dinh community-based tourism development of the Department of Tourism, People's Committees at all levels, the direction and guidance of the local government, and most importantly, the effort of local people learns from the experience of community-based tourism development models.

KEYWORDS: Potential, development, community tourism, travel resources, Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district.

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent modern life, the tourism demand has become popular in all social classes, creating an explosion in the global tourist market and pushing tourism to become a "smokeless industry". Travel and tourism are among the essential industries in the global economy, accounting for the highest proportion contributing to world Gross Domestic Product (GDP): 2.9 trillion USD (2019), while creating 300 million jobs worldwide [1]. This number would have increased if there had not been the Covid-19 pandemic. Tourism is the industry with the highest contribution to the GDP of developing and developed countries [2]. After the COVID-19 pandemic, every region globally recorded a substantial increase in international tourists.

In Vietnam, Resolution 08-NQ/TW, 16 January 2017, of the Politburo stated: "Developing tourism into a spearhead economic sector is an important strategic orientation for the country's development creates a driving force to promote the development of other industries and fields". On that basis, the tourism industry has strived and achieved many outstanding results. In 2019, Vietnam's tourism industry welcomed more than 18 million international visitors (an increase of 16.2%

compared to 2018), serving 85 million domestic visitors, and total revenue reached about 720,000 billion VND [4].

In recent years, community-based tourism has become a vital development trend in Vietnam. The term community-based tourism comes from village tourism since the 1970s. Tourists visit villages, learn about customs, wildlife, festivals, and explore ecosystems biodiversity, rugged terrain with high mountains and deep valleys but sparse population, and the challenging living and traveling conditions. At such times, these guests need assistance, such as directions to avoid getting lost, a place to stay overnight, and a place to eat, which local people have facilitated to help and provide services. At that time, tourists often called it a trip with the support of local people - this was the premise for developing community-based tourism [5].

Community tourism can be defined as "a type of tourism established, managed, and provided by local communities in a defined territory" [6]. More generally, community tourism is defined as "a type of tourism that is planned, developed, owned and managed by the community, for the community and guided by a decision-making process responsibility, access, ownership, benefits - all are collective" [6]. Thus, the purpose of community tourism is rationally exploit and save

natural resources, preserve heritage and culture, improve community life, eliminate hunger and reduce poverty, and create income for people and bringing increasing tourism revenue. At the same time, encouraging the participation of local communities with voluntary help helps them to be more proactive, respectful, and responsible towards tourism resources.

In the world, researches on community-based tourism are very popular, such as Guidelines for the Development of Community-based eco-tourism [7] of the World Wildlife Fund (2001); Effective Community-based Tourism: The Best Practice Handbook of the Center for Sustainable Tourism Collaborative Research, Griffith University: Mount Gravatt, Australia (2010) [8]; Successful community-based tourism in Africa (2020) [9] and many other studies such as [10], [11], [12],...

In Vietnam, there are many studies on community-based tourism, for example, community-based tourism in the northern mountainous region: community-based tourism in the northern mountainous region of Vietnam (a case study of Sa Seng village, Sapa, Lao Cai and Lac village, Mai Chau, Hoa Binh) in 2011 by Nguyen Thi Huong [13]; Current status and model of community-based tourism development in Thua Thien Hue (2021)[14]; Thesis on sustainable community tourism development from a theoretical perspective of stakeholders: a case study in the Northwest region of Vietnam by La Thi Bich Quang (2021) [15] and many other practical studies. Thus, community tourism is a developing trend in the world. Vietnam has many highly developed regions and community tourism destinations, such as the Northwest region. However, there has yet to be any research. There needs to be research on community tourism in Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district, Thai Nguyen province, although the potential for community tourism development here is extensive.

Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district is a midland and mountainous commune located in the southwest of Dinh Hoa district, about 70 km from the center of Thai Nguyen province, with mainly low mountains, dirt mountains, and upside-down hills, many old forests and relatively large, fertile fields with many rivers and streams [16]. As of December 31, 2022, the total population in Phu Dinh commune is 1551 households with 5959 people. There are five ethnic groups (Kinh, Tay, Nung, San Chi, Dao) living together, and over 90% are ethnic minorities. People make a living mainly from agriculture, forestry, and livestock production, with over 90% of their income [17]. During the resistance war, Phu Dinh commune was the center of the Dinh Hoa Safety Area National Relic (ATK). Nowadays, many sites there are classified as unique national historical sites. Besides, this place also has many scenic spots to attract tourists. With the potential and advantages mentioned above, Phu Dinh can thrive in community tourism. However,

community-based tourism development needs to be commensurate with the potential. There are still many difficulties and problems to be solved. Stemming from the above fact, we have chosen to research: "*The potential for community tourism development in Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district, Thai Nguyen province*".

2. RESEARCH METHODS

During the research process, we used some of the following methods:

- Collecting data and documents method: collecting decisions and resolutions on the socio-economic development of Dinh Hoa district and Phu Dinh commune. Inheriting information about the economy, culture, society, and tourism of Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district from specialized agencies and the People's Committee of Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district. After being collected, data will be analyzed and synthesized, and the results will be used to build a research overview, some parts of the research results, and a discussion.

- Survey method: The survey method is an online survey of tourists' needs and a direct survey of local people. The sample size calculation method was performed according to Taro Yamane (1967) [18]. The total research sample is 1,551 households (2022). Priority sampling locations are for areas with potential for community tourism development. With n being the sample size, N being the population number, e being the standard error, we have:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

With an error of 10%, we can calculate the number of votes to survey local people as 94 votes (actually 100 votes). The survey of visitors' needs was conducted online, so it was convenient. The number of survey votes collected was 134 votes. The survey subjects were from all walks of life and all walks of life. The survey results evaluate the potential for community tourism development in Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district, Thai Nguyen province.

- Statistical method: Based on the collected data and documents, conduct statistics to see the needs of tourists and the wishes of local people for community tourism development products.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS

3.1. Potential for community tourism development in Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district

The potential for community tourism development in Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district, can be divided into the potential of natural and supporting tourism resources. However, this division is only relative because a tourist destination can be natural and cultural tourism resources, such as the Khuon Tat banyan tree area.

3.1.1. Natural Tourism Resources

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Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district, has beautiful natural landscapes. The summer climate is quite extraordinary because this is an area with many green trees, rivers, and streams. A natural destination that attracts many tourists is Khuon Tat waterfall, a seven-floor waterfall in the middle of pristine mountains and forests. The waterfall is like a charming natural painting. Looking down from the top of De Pass, the waterfall is naturally created like stairs on stilts, with clear water pouring down and white foam all year round. Visitors here can bathe next to the cascading waterfalls, each cascading has cool tree shade, and on both sides of the stream are flat green lawns, an ideal place to camp and rest.

3.1.2. Humanistic tourism resources

Anyone who has visited Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district, will admit that this place is rich in humanistic tourism resources, from historical relics to artificial landscapes. When discussing historical relics, we discuss the ATK Dinh Hoa, "Capital of the mountain wind, Viet Bac war resistance zone". Viet Bac (Northern Vietnam) is a region of Vietnam north of Hanoi that served as the Viet Minh's base of support during the First Indochina War (1946–1954). Viet Bac is also called the capital of northernmost Vietnam because this area was the location of the headquarters of the Communist Party of Vietnam at the period before the rising against French domination in 1945, and the location of the headquarters of the Việt Minh government during the war of resistance against the French colonialists.

Viet Bac was the area where President Ho Chi Minh and the Party Central Committee and Government lived, worked to lead the resistance war against French colonialism (1946 - 1954), which decided the country's important issues to victory, ending the war and restoring peace in Indochina. There was a complex of the Vietnamese people's most important revolutionary historical relics in the 20th century, with meaning and value in many aspects. On 5 May 2012, the Prime Minister signed Decision No. 548/QĐ-TTg, classifying the Dinh Hoa Safe Zone historical relic as a remarkable National Monument. Some tourist destinations not to be missed when coming to Phu Dinh include:

President Ho Chi Minh Memorial House is a place of gratitude, expressing the respect of the country's people, overseas Vietnamese, and international friends to beloved Uncle Ho. The project was built in a prime location, "Left dragon, right white tiger", with the traditional communal house and temple architecture, inaugurated on the 115th anniversary of Uncle Ho's birthday (19 May 1890 - 19 May 2005). In the main hall, in a solemn position, is the statue of President Ho Chi Minh made of gold-plated bronze, weighing 4 tons. Above the statue is the hammer and sickle symbol, embossed golden star, and parallel couplets. Below the main hall is a place to show movies and display documents and artifacts about the life and activities of President Ho Chi

Minh. Many trees are planted around the memorial house, creating a landscape and fresh air.

The ATK Exhibition House was built and inaugurated on the 50th anniversary of Uncle Ho's return to live and work at ATK Dinh Hoa (20 May 1947 - 20 May 1997). Nearly 400 documents and artifacts about the revolutionary life of President Ho Chi Minh and comrades who led the Party and State during the years of resistance against the French colonialists (1946 - 1954) were kept there.

Tin Keo Relic is where Uncle Ho lived and worked many times to lead the national resistance. In Keo Province, on 6 December 1953, President Ho Chi Minh chaired a Politburo conference, and the Party Central Committee decided to open the historic Dien Bien Phu campaign, approving the people's combat plan which achieved a "splendid victory in five continents, shaking the earth". Tin Keo Relic is one of the most important relics in the system of historical revolutionary relics of ATK Dinh Hoa, of the Viet Bac war resistance zone.

Khuon Tat relic includes Uncle Ho's stilt house, living and working at Na Dinh Hill, Khuon Tat banyan tree, and Tat slope, where Uncle Ho used to fish and bathe. On behalf of the Politburo at the stilt house on Na Dinh Hill, President Ho Chi Minh assigned General Commander Vo Nguyen Giap, Secretary of the Party Committee, and commander of the Dien Bien Phu campaign before leaving for the battle. Khuon Tat banyan tree was where Uncle Ho and his warriors protected and helped practice dangerous martial arts and polish. The Banyan tree is located in the center of the Khuon Tat area with ample land airy space. Khuon Tat banyan tree has luxuriant leaves, a body of five or six people hugging, and is about 40 - 50m high.

Relic of the Hill of Ordain Generals: On May 28, 1948, the Government of the Democratic Republic of Vietnam displayed and celebrated the Military Rank Ceremony. President Ho Chi Minh, on behalf of the Vietnamese Government, conferred the rank of General to General Vo Nguyen Giap. There, President Ho Chi Minh also announced the decree conferring the rank of Major General to comrades: Tran Tu Binh, Van Tien Dung, Le Thiet Hung, Le Hien Mai, Tran Dai Nghia, Hoang Sam, Nguyen Son, Chu Van Tan, Hoang Van Thai.

ATK Dinh Hoa is a complex of the most important relics of the Vietnamese people in the 20th century, an anti-war capital with relic sites: Pac Bo (Cao Bang), Tan Trao, Chiem Hoa, Son Duong, Yen Son (Tuyen Quang), ATK Dinh Hoa (Thai Nguyen), Cho Don (Bac Kan) have historical significance and value in many aspects. In particular, ATK Dinh Hoa is the place to initiate and direct the Dien Bien Phu campaign to win, end the war, and restore peace in Indochina...

ATK Dinh Hoa Flower Garden can be considered as the first community tourism activity site in Phu Dinh commune created by human hands. This place has a very convenient

location in the middle of the cluster of Khuon Tat relics. The flower garden is located on the slope of the Khuon Tat River, where Uncle Ho and the soldiers protecting Uncle used to bathe. ATK Dinh Hoa flower garden grows healthy seasonal flowers. In the middle of the garden is Tay Ethnic wooden floor house - a clean wooden floor house but simple. The 2nd floor is a place to stay (maximum number of 30 guests), and the first floor is a place to play, drink tea, and enjoy local products that are beautifully decorated and clean. Next to the stilt house, there is also a small stage for performing arts and not causing fires. Above the stilt house is a vase of fruit trees of all kinds, such as mango, pomelo, apple, sapodilla, litchi, longan, and peach of the Dao ethnic group. With fresh air, beautiful scenery, space of mountains, forests, and rivers surrounded by birdsong and flowers, ATK Dinh Hoa is an ideal place for tourists to both visit ATK Dinh Hoa historical Site. You can experience the experience of discovering the lives of local people, enjoying the days of relaxation in the Son Chan region.

Tea Hill in Phu Ninh Hamlet is one of the most famous tea areas in the Dinh Hoa district. The traditional tea craft village spans nearly 47 hectares and has undergone significant changes since the end of 2019. The Korea Saemaul Undong New Rural Globalization Fund (SGF) has developed and built Phu Ninh hamlet as the new rural hamlet and Saemaul new village model.

The appearance of the new countryside of Phu Ninh hamlet has changed significantly, especially the green tea fields, which are cultivated according to VietGap standards. The roads to the tea fields are paved with clean concrete, and the tea beds are neatly and technically trimmed. The tea drying area is clean and equipped with tea drying machines by gas and green tea crumple machines.

Currently, the number of tourists visiting the ATK Dinh Hoa Historical Relic Area combines experience. Experience picking tea and performing tea processing steps in Phu Ninh Hamlet is increasingly crowded, especially for young children in the city and foreign tourists. However, accommodation services here have yet to be invested and developed, so currently, there are no accommodation service facilities.

Long Tong Festival: In the Tay and Nung languages, "going down to the field" is called "the cage of existence". The Long Tong festival is a typical traditional religious activity of the Tay people, such as the Kinh people's still-field ceremony, held in villages to pray for favorable weather and green trees, bountiful season, increase in fertility, everyone is happy, the village is peaceful. Although it is a festival of the Tay people, the largest ethnic minority group in Thai Nguyen province, the Long Tong festival has gathered. The unique cultural nuances of other ethnic groups, such as Nung, San Chi, and Dao, have become a unique festival of Tay and Nung ethnic groups, the biggest Spring festival of Thai Nguyen province,

attracting more and more attention crowded with local tourists and many other places. In Thai Nguyen province, the Long Tong festival is usually held on November 10 and 11. The biggest and most special festival is the Deo De village, Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district.

One of the Human tourism resources that must be mentioned is local food. At Phu Dinh, the local cuisine is typical of the ethnic groups in the North, with familiar dishes such as sticky rice in bamboo, five-color sticky rice, stew pork, Cooc mo cake, black Chung cake, wild hill chicken, and wild village pig. This traditional dish is also a tourist attraction and brings unforgettable experiences for visitors.

3.1.3. Additional resources supported

Roads: Although it is a mountainous commune, Phu Dinh commune is located in a safe zone and is the capital of the resistance war, so the Party and Government are very interested in developing roads. Routes from National Disclosure 3 to the social center have just been expanded and renewed in 2023. The roads from the district center to the communes, villages, and hamlets have been paved with asphalt, which is very convenient for traveling, trading, and attracting tourists.

Besides, the project on community tourism development in the Khuon Tat area, Phu Dinh commune (2022-2025), is also developing and constructing additional supporting services, such as building a new beach, parking, toilets, reception points, display centers, providing community tourism information, supporting the construction of new community tourism storage facilities, real-life food restaurants, consolidated display, introduced introduction, sold souvenirs and local specialties, supported investment in garbage collection equipment at community tourist sites.

3.2. Current status and need for community tourism development in Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district

3.2.1. General overview of the tourism development situation of Phu Dinh commune

In 2019, Phu Dinh commune tourism had substantial changes with many positive results. The number of tourists coming to Phu Dinh increased continuously compared to 2018 to 2,680 tourist groups with nearly 557,000 visitors. However, tourists visiting Phu Dinh visit historical sites, not experience community tourism. In 2020, due to the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic, the total number of tourist arrivals decreased significantly, reaching 226,699 visitors, down 40.7% over the same period, reaching 55.8% of the year plan. Of these, 193,606 are domestic and 33,093 international visitors [19]. It can be seen that the COVID-19 pandemic has greatly affected tourism service businesses in Phu Dinh commune. Some establishments must request dissolution or temporary suspension of operations. In order to cope with the epidemic, the province has implemented many tourism stimulus programs with discount packages and service promotions to boost domestic tourism demand. The

agreements between travel companies develop intra-provincial tour programs with promotional prices, tour discounts, and electricity discounts for tourist accommodation establishments.

In 2022, infrastructure serving Phu Dinh tourism development will also receive strong investment attention, such as the road system, especially implementing the community tourism development project associated with conservation and promotion. Traditional cultural and historical values of ethnic groups in Dinh Hoa district in 2021-2025, with a vision to 2030 implemented in Khuon Tat village, is a great driving force to help this place develop community tourism. Institutions Accommodation and tourist attractions have increased investment in facilities, improved service quality, diversified tourism products, and better linked with tourism businesses inside and outside the province. Investment promotion and advertising activities began to be powerfully deployed.

Currently, the development of community tourism in Phu Dinh commune is only in the early stages. Only a few households have invested in enough facilities and human resources to serve the community's needs, such as accommodation, food, rest, and enjoying local culture.

On the side of the Khuon Tat, Phu Ninh agricultural cooperative, Phu Dinh commune quickly caught the trend. The interest of tourists when coming to Phu Dinh is to visit and experience tea areas. Therefore, this facility has taken advantage of available advantages to build and operate the tea culture space since 2021. However, the number of visitors who experience agricultural tourism services is still not much.

3.2.2. Current status and needs of community tourism development in Phu Dinh commune

To analyze the current status and development needs of community-based tourism in Phu Dinh commune, we use the survey method, survey by questionnaire about tourists' needs for community-based tourism, and survey local communities' understanding of community-based tourism, the difficulties and challenges they face when implementing community-based tourism activities.

3.2.2.1. Survey sample characteristics

a. Characteristics of the tourist survey sample

The total number of guests surveyed was 134 people. Characteristics of the survey sample are as follows: Regarding gender, there were 91 men, accounting for 67.9%, and 40 women, accounting for 29.8%; There were 03 people (2.2%) who did not provide information. Regarding age, the focus is mainly from 18 - 28 years old: 89 people (66.4%), the age group 29 - 39 years old: 27 people (20.1%). Other ages account for a low percentage. Regarding educational level, they were focusing mainly on high school and University/Postgraduate levels. These two groups accounted for 72.4%. The Intermediate/College level accounts for 18%.

Other educational qualification groups account for a very low percentage.

Regarding the occupation of the surveyed people, the highest proportion is the number of business guests (26.2%) and students (25.7%), followed by workers (17.5%) and officials (11.7%). Other occupations account for a low percentage.

b. Survey characteristics of the population sample

The total number of survey samples is 100 votes, representing households in Phu Dinh commune. Survey characteristics are as follows:

Regarding gender, 53 men scored 53%; 47 females used 47%.

Regarding age, the lowest is 21 years old, the highest is 81 years old, Average age is 36.8 years old. Regarding ethnicity, the Kinh ethnic group has 48 people, accounting for 48%; the Tay ethnic group has 35 people, accounting for 35%; the Dao ethnic group has 17 people, accounting for 17%. Regarding the learning process, the highest use of technology is in secondary school learning facilities (secondary school): 43 people (43%), primary school students 34 people (34%), and high school information students: 12 people (12%), other levels use low rates. Regarding occupations, most interviewees worked in agriculture (71%), business in tourism-related services (13%), and the remainder were in other occupations.

3.2.2.2. Tourist needs for community tourism in Phu Dinh commune

Through the investigation, tourists know about Phu Dinh commune tourist attractions mainly through the Internet (32.1%), relatives and friends (29.8%), television (11.2%), and tourism publications (9.7%), through from travel companies (7.5%), through newspapers, magazines (3.7%), and from other sources (6.0%). The survey shows that exploiting tourist information in the 4.0 revolution era has its characteristics. It also shows that tourism promotion and promotion work needs to be innovated to achieve greater efficiency. Regarding the number of times visitors come to Phu Dinh, 32.1% of visitors came for the first time, 17.1% of second-time visitors, 26.1% for the third; 24.7% came for the fourth time or more, showing that Phu Dinh has great appeal to tourists. Regarding the purpose of traveling, the primary purposes are a combination of sightseeing, work, and meetings (29.1%), study, research (26.1%), spirituality, and belief (20.1%), working and meetings (14.9%), and the lowest is for sightseeing and relaxation purposes (9.0%). These data show that tourists only visit, study, and work at the ATK Dinh Hoa Historical Relic Area locations; other types of tourism, especially community tourism, still need to be developed. In order to get opinions on tourists' satisfaction with community tourism in Phu Dinh commune, the survey was designed on a 5-level Likert scale [20] (1: Completely disagree; 2: Poor; 3: Average; 4: Good; 5: Very Good). That

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scale can be synthesized into 5 rating levels, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Summary of rating levels according to the Likert scale

Evaluation level	Average point	Results
Level 1	1,00 – 1,80	Very poor
Level 2	1,81 – 2,60	Poor
Level 3	2,61 – 3,40	Average
Level 4	3,41 – 4,20	Good
Level 5	4,21 – 5,00	Very good

The first evaluation criterion for community tourism is an attractive factor for developing community tourism in Phu Dinh commune. Survey results show that tourists' general assessment of attractive factors for developing community

tourism in Phu Dinh commune is outstanding (4.21 points). The criteria are scored according to the specific Linkert scale in Table 2.

Table 2. Attractive factors for community tourism development

Criteria	Average score	Conclusion
Unique historical site	4,7	Very good
Unique cultural identity	3,2	Average
Attractive specialties	4,06	Good
Beautiful scenery	4,2	Good
Good Fresh air	4,5	Very good
Hospitality of the people	4,6	Very good
Overall rating	4,21	Very good

Regarding infrastructure, the overall rating of tourists is 3.76

points, equivalent to a reasonable level. The specific scoring criteria are shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Assessment of infrastructure for community tourism development

Criteria	Average Score	Conclusion
Convenient access to tourist attractions	4.2	Good
Public toilets ensure good tourist service	4.1	Good
The power supply system ensures good tourism service	3.9	Good
Water supply system ensures good tourism service	3.9	Good
The communication system ensures good tourism service	3.3	Average
Transport has good quality	3.2	Average
Overall rating	3.76	Good

Regarding the quality of community tourism products and services, the most highly rated criteria are: tourists can

experience local life, and the tourist area has many attractive attractions. Overall rating: Good (table 4).

Table 4. Evaluation of the quality of community tourism products and services

Criteria	Average Score	Conclusion
Diverse tourism products and services	3.23	Average
Attractive tourism products and services	3.39	Average
The tourist area has many attractive attractions	4.7	Very good
Spacious and airy reception area for guests	3.2	Average
The dishes are unique and attractive to tourists	3.9	Good
Catering service ensures food hygiene and safety	4.0	Good
Food service has good quality	3.8	Good
Homestay services (staying at homestays) have good quality	3.76	Good
Tourists get to experience local life	4.8	Very good
Well-organized tourist transportation service	3.61	Good
Overall rating	3.84	Good

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Evaluating people serving community tourism, the average score achieved is 3.9 points. Specific criteria are presented in Table 5.

Table 5. Evaluation of people serving community tourism

Criteria	Average Score	Conclusion
Always friendly and welcoming to guests	4.29	Very good
Ready to help, meet customer requests	3.93	Good
Have good tourism knowledge and skills	3.62	Good
Have good communication skills	4.64	Very good
Listen and promptly resolve customer complaints	3.71	Good
Dress and dress politely and elegantly	3.36	Medium
Customers always feel confident and satisfied	3.80	Good
Overall rating	3.90	Good

In evaluating security and safety in tourism, the average score is 3.79 points at a reasonable level. The specific criteria are as follows (table 6).

Table 6. Evaluating security and safety in tourism

Criteria	Average Score	Conclusion
No begging situation	4.65	Very good
There is no street vendor situation	2.5	Poor
There is no situation of coaxing or coercing customers	3.7	Good
No theft	3.67	Good
No superstition	4.0	Good
There is no jostling, pushing, or disorder	3.92	Good
Guests always feel happy and comfortable	4.1	Good
Overall rating	3.79	Good

Regarding the price of tourism services, the criteria do not differ much, all scoring from 4.5 to 4.8, with an overall rating of 4.62 points, specifically as follows (Table 7).

Table 7. Evaluation of tourism service prices

Criteria	Average Score	Conclusion
Reasonable accommodation price	4.8	Very good
Reasonable food prices	4.5	Very good
Reasonable shopping prices	4.5	Very good
Reasonable price for sightseeing services	4.7	Very good
Overall rating	4.62	Very good

The satisfaction level of tourists is as follows: satisfaction rate accounted for 62.9%; Very satisfied accounts for 18.8%. Guests with standard reviews account for 12%, the remaining rate of dissatisfied and very dissatisfied guests accounts for only 2.7%, and the remaining 3.6% need to provide more information. Since then, the number of guests planning to return to Phu Dinh has been very high: 41.8% of guests plan to return, and 23.9% of guests plan to return. The intention to introduce tourists to friends and relatives is also high: 45.5% of tourists intend to introduce; 23.9% of visitors intend to introduce Phu Dinh tourism to friends and relatives.

3.2.2.3. Knowledge and difficulties of local communities about community-based tourism development

Of the total of 100 surveyed households, 13 are engaged in tourism, accounting for 13%; 87 households do not do tourism, accounting for 87%. Among the households working in tourism, the household has the earliest time working in tourism since 2012. The types of jobs involved in tourism are diverse, such as catering and accommodation business. If

including the food and drink business, there are two households. The rest are other types of businesses, such as selling souvenirs, food, and water.

Regarding welcoming guests of 13 tourism business households, two welcome guests regularly (15.38%), and eleven welcome guests irregularly (84.62%). Regarding the length of stay of visitors, according to the survey, most visitors arrive during the day, accounting for 59.4%; visitors from 2-3 days accounted for 36.2%; Visitors visiting for 1-2 hours only account for 4.4%. According to households, tourists visit ATK historical and cultural relics, enjoy food, experience people's lives, buy specialties, and visit the mountains. Other activities account for a low proportion. Regarding the revenue from tourism households, two households answered that the average income is 181.4 million VND/year, the lowest is 30 million VND/year, and the highest is 340 million VND/year. Regarding the number of people trained in tourism in households, most people can only participate in short-term training courses organized by the commune.

Regarding difficulties in tourism development for households, there were 79 responses. Regarding the difficulties in developing community-based tourism, the households said that the most significant difficulty is the need for more investment capital for accommodation establishments, young human resources, and a lack of experienced and qualified human resources. There needs to be coordination with the travel company, no support or management role of the local government. The households operate spontaneously to compete with each other. Tourists come only once and do not return. Human resources of working age are currently mainly working as workers and agriculture. In addition, 9% of households answered that there were no difficulties.

Regarding the level of satisfaction with the current job, there are 48 respondents, of which 89.6% are satisfied, and 10.4% are not satisfied with the current job. Regarding the tourism development plan, there were 28 responses, of which seven households plan to maintain the current status, five plan to invest in expansion, and one does not plan to do tourism. Fifteen households intend to participate in tourism in the future. The activities expected to participate are food and beverage business 31.9%, sales to tourists 22.3%, and other activities.

Regarding the desire to be supported when participating in tourism, the desire to receive support in terms of capital accounts for the highest proportion, followed by Knowledge and skills in tourism about legal proceedings.

3.3. Proposing some products to develop community tourism in Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district

Based on the tourism potential and needs of tourists and local reality, we propose several products for community tourism development in the study area as follows:

- Agricultural tourism and craft village experience products: sightseeing combined with experience in tea processing, rice transplanting, and harvesting.
- Culinary tourism products combined with the experience of preparing traditional dishes such as sticky rice in bamboo, five-color sticky rice, stew pork, Cooc mo cake, black Chung cake, sticky rice steamed with tea leaves, Stir-fried horse/buffalo meat with tea buds, steamed fish with tea leaves, fried beans with green tea powder.
- Traditional cultural experience tourism products: Tay ethnic, Dao, and San Chi.

4. CONCLUSION

From the results of evaluating community tourism activities in Phu Dinh commune, we draw the following conclusions: Phu Dinh commune, Dinh Hoa district, Thai Nguyen province, has great potential for community tourism development because it has essential historical, humanistic, and attractive natural tourism resources. However, community tourism development here is only at the

beginning due to difficulties such as lack of capital, experienced and qualified human resources, and lack of connection between businesses and tourism households community.

Since 2022, the community tourism development project has been implemented in Phu Dinh commune. People are also increasingly interested in investing in facilities and human resources for community tourism development revenue from tourism. The calendar is getting higher and higher and plays an essential role in developing the local economy and improving people's lives in the commune.

Based on tourism resources and tourists' needs, we propose several community tourism products in Phu Dinh commune mainly related to agricultural experience activities, cuisine, and traditional crafts of the people here. From this study, we propose some directions and solutions to develop community tourism in Phu Dinh commune:

- Enhance local communities' capacity, helping them be the subjects of preserving humanistic tourism resources and actively participating in tourism to improve the economy.
- Improve service quality for tourists and expand community tourist attractions. Focus on investing in facilities and diversifying tourism products to meet the diverse needs of tourists.
- Exploitation goes hand in hand with conservation: while the number of guests is increasing, the local community still preserves the fresh air environment, natural tourism resources, and cultural identity of the nation.

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